

ANALYSIS OF THE FREQUENCY STABILITY HISTORY OF GPS NAVSTAR CLOCKS

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ABSTRACT

The two-sample Allan variance has been the standard metric for assessing the frequency stability of atomic clocks which may be characterized by nonstationary noise processes. The convergence of the Allan variance for the noise types typical of atomic clocks might appear to suggest that the variance could be estimated to an arbitrary degree of accuracy by processing more data over longer and longer periods of time, which would lead to progressively smaller confidence intervals. This tacit assumption, however, was called into question because of the behavior of one of the Global Positioning System (GPS) on-orbit Navstar atomic clocks whose frequency stability profile exhibited significant change with the processing of additional data. Because of the peculiar nonstationary behavior of this clock, a model for the frequency stability history was developed and is now incorporated as a routine part of the analysis of Navstar clocks conducted by the Naval Research Laboratory (NRL).[†]

The frequency stability history corresponds to the output of an N-sample moving average filter operating on the sequence of squared first differences of the M-day frequency offset measurements. This procedure assumes that the stochastic process has increments whose second order properties are slowly evolving over time such that, to a reasonable approximation, it has stationary increments over the N sample interval.

Frequency stability histories are presented using from one to 120-sample averages—the number of samples averaged representing a compromise between the time resolution and the stability of the estimate. Included are frequency stability histories for both cesium and rubidium on-orbit Navstar clocks. The results indi-

cate that the frequency stability of most of the Navstar clocks is invariant over the useful life of the clock, that the frequency stability of some of the clocks degrades over the life of the clock, and that the frequency stability of still others improves after an initial transient. The frequency stability history is now used to detect and measure degradation in the frequency stability. Significant changes in the frequency stability are reported to the GPS Master Control Station (MCS).

INTRODUCTION

The primary purpose of this paper is to present results for several Navstar clocks that have been continuously operated on-orbit for time spans of up to nine years. Since the Navstar clocks should be capable of operating on-orbit for many years, it is not surprising that small changes in the frequency stability could occur. NRL routinely analyzes the long-term performance [1] of all Navstar and monitor station clocks. *Figure 1* presents the information flow from a single Navstar space vehicle (SV) to each of the GPS monitor stations (MS).

Figure 1

[†] This work was sponsored by the GPS Joint Program Office.

Currently, five Air Force monitor stations are used to passively track each operational Navstar SV in the GPS constellation, collecting pseudorange and pseudorange rate data from each SV. Corrections are made for ionospheric and tropospheric delay using either a model or dual-frequency measurements, and are further made for relativistic effects and earth rotation. The tracking data collected at each MS is sent to the MCS where the Navstar SV ephemeris and clock parameters are estimated and predicted. The MCS periodically uploads to each Navstar SV the ephemeris and clock data, which is then included as part of the broadcast GPS navigation message. Additional measurements—collected at the U.S. Naval Observatory (USNO) precise-time station—are referenced to the Department of Defense (DoD) master clock and are used for determining the steering of GPS time.

All clock offset measurements to be presented in this analysis are referenced to the DoD master clock. The position of the Navstar SV at the time of measurement is computed using either the broadcast or the post-processed precise ephemeris. The clock offset values for each Navstar SV clock are then obtained by smoothing for either 13- or 15-minute intervals.

Given two clock offset measurements, denoted by $x(t_j)$ and $x(t_k)$, sampled at times t_j and t_k , the sample time τ is defined as $\tau = (t_j - t_k)$. The average fractional frequency offset, $\bar{y}(t) = \frac{x(t_j) - x(t_k)}{\tau}$, is computed using successive clock offset measurements. These clock offset measurements will subsequently be used to compute frequency offset histories, frequency stability profiles, and frequency stability histories for the Navstar clocks, using sample times of one-sidereal day, or more.

FREQUENCY STABILITY

NRL currently employs two measures of frequency stability in the time domain analysis of the Navstar clocks: (1) the Allan variance, and (2) the Hadamard variance. The Allan variance is employed primarily in the analysis of the cesium clocks, while the Hadamard variance is employed in the analysis of the rubidium clocks that are known to exhibit significant drift (clock aging) coefficients.

The Allan variance is estimated using a finite number of uniformly sampled frequency offsets by the following equation:

$$\sigma_y^2(\tau) \simeq \frac{1}{2(M-1)} \sum_{k=1}^{M-1} (\bar{y}_{k+1} - \bar{y}_k)^2$$

The average frequency offsets are computed by using pairs of clock offset measurements separated by sample time τ . The square root of this two-sample variance, $\sigma_y(\tau)$, is known as the *Allan deviation*. This time-

domain frequency stability measure is independent of initial clock offset and initial frequency offset. The slope of the frequency stability estimates, plotted as a function of sample time, can be used to identify the dominant type of noise that is present in the clock data.

The Hadamard variance is estimated using the following equation:

$${}_H\sigma_y^2(\tau) \simeq \frac{1}{6(M-2)} \sum_{k=1}^{M-2} (\bar{y}_{k+2} - 2\bar{y}_{k+1} + \bar{y}_k)^2$$

The Hadamard variance, like the Allan variance, is independent of initial clock offset and initial frequency offset, with the additional feature of being independent of initial frequency drift (aging). The square root of this two-sample variance, ${}_H\sigma_y(\tau)$, is known as the *Hadamard deviation*.

If the random process was truly stationary, then the frequency stability computations could be performed using all of the clock data, or could be estimated using any finite subset without reference to the epoch of the measurements. Prior to the discovery in 1989 that one of the Navstar cesium clocks had changed frequency stability, the default technique was to process the clock data using all available measurements. Subsequent to this determination, an algorithm was developed to detect and measure any change in frequency stability. NRL currently estimates and reports the frequency stability of all Navstar clocks on a quarterly basis.

FREQUENCY STABILITY HISTORY

The model used to test the invariance of the frequency stability is known as the frequency-stability time history. The frequency stability history is computed as the output of an N-day moving average filter operating on the sequence of squared first differences of the one-day frequency offset measurements. The “moving average” technique is one which bases its estimates on the most recent finite set of past measurements. As a new measurement is taken in, the oldest measurement of the set is dropped.

Two models of the frequency stability history are currently used by NRL to analyze the Navstar cesium and rubidium clocks. The first, a moving average model of the Allan variance, is used to continuously measure the frequency stability of the Navstar cesium clocks as a function of time. The argument for the moving average Allan variance is the squared first difference of the frequency offset. The second type of model employs a moving average of the Hadamard variance. The argument for the moving average Hadamard variance is the squared second difference of the frequency offset.

These frequency stability history models incorporate the assumption that the stochastic process has

increments whose second order properties are slowly changing over time in such a way that it has stationary increments over an N-point interval. The number of samples used to compute the frequency stability history effectively represents a tradeoff between the number of samples and the time span used to compute the frequency stability estimate.

Five Navstar SV clocks—two Block I cesiums, two Block II cesiums, and one Block II rubidium—will be used to present examples that characterize the frequency stability performance of the clocks as a function of time.

NAVSTAR 10 CESIUM

The first example presented uses data that was collected for the Navstar 10 cesium clock (serial no. 5) that was operated for 7.3 years, beginning on 11 October, 1984 (MJD 45984) until 6 February, 1992 (MJD 48658). The frequency offset history, presented by Figure 2, shows that the initial frequency offset was 6.6×10^{-12} ; and, at the end of the 7.3 year span, the frequency offset was -3.4×10^{-12} .

Figure 2

This clock exhibited an overall negative trend in frequency offset with two significant changes in drift. The first change occurred on 29 April 1988 (MJD 47280) after 3.6 years of operation, and the second change occurred on 8 July 1990 (MJD 48080), some 2.2 years later. The drift appeared to be constant for the remaining 1.5 years of operation. In addition to the changes in drift, this clock also exhibited significant changes in frequency stability. The change in frequency stability of this Navstar 10 cesium clock can be demonstrated by computing the residuals to an eleven-sample moving average filter that was applied to the one-day frequency offset data as presented by Figure 3. Comparison of the frequency offset

residuals observed during 1985 with those obtained during 1991 offers the most visible proof that nonstationary behavior had occurred in this clock. This change in frequency stability will now be detected through the use of the frequency stability history model, after first presenting the effect that the number of variance samples has on the “smoothness” of the frequency stability history estimates.

Figure 3

Figures 4-7 present four plots of the frequency stability history using 1, 5, 30, and 120 samples that are used to study the effect that the number of samples averaged has on the frequency stability estimates.

Figure 4

FREQUENCY STABILITY HISTORY OF
NAVSTAR 10 CESIUM CLOCK
DoD Master Clock (SPS)
Sample Time: 1 day Sample Size: 5

Figure 5

FREQUENCY STABILITY HISTORY OF
NAVSTAR 10 CESIUM CLOCK
DoD Master Clock (SPS)
Sample Time: 1 day Sample Size: 30

Figure 6

FREQUENCY STABILITY HISTORY OF
NAVSTAR 10 CESIUM CLOCK
DoD Master Clock (SPS)
Sample Time: 1 day Sample Size: 120

Figure 7

The results show that a preliminary estimate of a Navstar clock's frequency stability can be obtained using five samples (that require one week of once per day clock offset data); however, a larger number of samples are required to smoothly follow the frequency stability behavior. Reference to Figure 7 shows that 120 samples provide a smooth estimate of a Navstar clock's frequency stability history.

Further analysis of the Navstar 10 cesium frequency stability history for a 120-sample average, presented by Figure 7, and the frequency offset history, presented by Figure 2, indicates that three "stationary increments" can be identified: (1) MJD 45984-47280, (2) MJD 47280-48080, and (3) MJD 48080-48658. Figure 8 presents the segmented frequency stability profile with three resultant profiles, one for each stationary increment. The three profiles are graphically monotonic, with the best performance obtained during the first segment that corresponds to the first 3.6 years of operation; the least-stable performance was observed during the third segment for the final 1.5 years of operation of this cesium clock.

SEGMENTED FREQUENCY STABILITY OF
NAVSTAR 10 CESIUM CLOCK
DoD Master Clock (SPS)
11 October 1984 to 7 February 1992

Figure 8

NAVSTAR 9 CESIUM

The second example presented uses data that was collected from the Navstar 9 cesium clock (serial no. 4) that was operated for 9.3 years—from 13 July 1984 (MJD 45894) until 12 October 1993 (MJD 49272). The Navstar 9 SV is a Block I spacecraft that was launched on 13 June 1984. The Selective Availability feature of GPS was not implemented on the Block I Navstar SVs; therefore no correction was required for this effect. Clock offsets for this cesium clock at one-day intervals were computed using pseudorange measurements collected with a single-frequency GPS time-transfer receiver located at

the USNO precise time station with time and frequency inputs obtained from the DoD master clock. The frequency offset history for the Navstar 9 cesium clock during its 9.3 years of operation is presented by *Figure 9*.

Figure 9

The frequency stability history for the Navstar 9 cesium clock is presented by *Figure 10* using a 120-sample average and the Allan variance as an estimator. The most notable feature in the frequency stability results, evaluated for a one-day sample time, is that this clock performed at a frequency stability that was estimated to be better than 2×10^{-13} for more than 8 years.

Figure 10

The frequency stability history results and the frequency offset history results were analyzed to identify “stationary increments” for this clock. Three segments were determined: (1) from 13 July 1984 until 29 April 1988 (3.8 years), (2) 29 April 1988 until 16 August 1992 (4.3 years), and (3) 16 August, 1992 until 13 July 1993 (0.9 years). The segmented frequency stability history for the Navstar 9 cesium clock is presented by *Figure 11* using three segments.

Figure 11

The first two frequency stability profiles are almost identical, with the dominant noise type observed to be white frequency noise for sample times of up to ten days. The third time segment indicated a decrease in performance as compared to the first two profiles. The third frequency stability profile was estimated for an eleven-month span, using data from from 16 August 1992 until 13 July 1993. The one-day frequency stability estimate was 2.3×10^{-13} .

The frequency stability history results presented for the Navstar 9 cesium clock indicate that the frequency stability of this clock was essentially invariant for more than 8 years. Analysis of the three frequency stability profiles indicates that the dominant noise type for this cesium clock during the entire nine-year useful life span was white frequency noise for sample times of one-day to ten-days.

NAVSTAR 15 RESULTS

The third example presented uses data collected from the Block II Navstar 15 cesium clock (serial no. 37). The clock data is presented in two segments that further demonstrate the necessity for the frequency stability history. *Figure 12* presents a one-year frequency

offset history for the Navstar 15 cesium clock beginning with its initial activation on 16 October 1990.

Figure 12

The clock offset values were computed using measurements collected at USNO with a dual-frequency PPS receiver that was operated in the single frequency mode, and used the ionospheric model contained in the GPS navigation message to compute the ionospheric corrections. The Navstar 15 orbital positions were computed using the broadcast ephemeris. The effect of the broadcast ephemeris on the clock offset measurements [2] has been shown to be a white phase noise process that appears in the data as a small increase in measurement noise. The frequency offsets were computed using clock offsets that were separated in sample time by one day and are plotted as the ordinate in Figure 12, expressed in Parts Per (pp) 10^{12} . Two time axes are presented: the lower time axis presents the Modified Julian Day (MJD), while the upper time axis presents the corresponding calendar dates.

The frequency offset values presented by Figure 12 were subsequently used to compute the mean frequency offset of the Navstar 15 cesium clock from the DoD master clock during the first year of operation. The mean frequency offset was $-0.7 \text{ pp}10^{12}$, indicating close agreement with the expected value for Navstar cesium clocks.

The frequency stability profile for the Navstar 15 cesium clock, presented by Figure 13, was computed using the Allan variance as the frequency stability model, with sample times that varied from one day to 36 days. The maximum sample time employed in the frequency stability calculations was 36 days, a value equal to 1/10 of the data length (one year) to insure a reasonable confidence in the frequency stability estimates. For a one-day sample time, the estimated frequency stability was

1.8×10^{-13} . For sample times of one to eight days, the slope of the frequency stability profile is nominally $-1/2$, indicating that the dominant random noise type is white frequency noise. For a 36-day sample time, the frequency stability was estimated to be 3.3×10^{-14} .

Figure 13

The one-sigma confidence intervals for each frequency stability estimate presented by Figure 13 were computed for a white frequency noise process. Note that the upper one-sigma confidence limits are slightly larger than the lower one-sigma confidence limits. For a 36-day sample time the upper confidence limit multiplier was computed to be 1.30; the corresponding upper one-sigma frequency stability estimate was 4.3×10^{-14} .

The next frequency stability profile for the Navstar 15 cesium clock is presented by Figure 14, using all of the data that was collected during the first two years of operation.

Figure 14

It was expected that the only notable difference would be an improvement in the confidence of the frequency stability estimates; however, it appeared that a significant difference had occurred.

The frequency offset history for the Navstar 15 cesium clock from 16 October 1990 to 11 November 1992 is presented in *Figure 15*. These frequency offset values were used to compute the mean offset of this clock from the DoD master clock. The mean of the frequency offset data was $-0.6 \text{ pp}10^{12}$, with a change of only $1 \text{ pp}10^{13}$ when compared to the first one-year dataset. However, note that the frequency offset residuals show a distinct trend about the mean frequency offset, indicating a departure from a white noise process.

Figure 15

The frequency stability history for the Navstar 15 clock is presented by *Figure 16*, using the one-day frequency offset values that were averaged for 120 samples.

Figure 16

The resultant frequency stability history shows that the Navstar 15 cesium clock initially had a one-day frequency stability of 2×10^{-13} , then improved until mid-1991, followed by a gradual increase to 2×10^{-13} early in 1992. During the last several months of operation of this clock, the frequency stability estimates gradually approached 3×10^{-13} for a one-day sample time.

NAVSTAR 24 RUBIDIUM & 29 CESIUM

The last example presented for the frequency stability history analysis uses data from two Block IIA clocks: first a rubidium clock, and second, for the purpose of comparison of the two clock types, a cesium clock. *Figure 18* presents the dual-frequency-offset histories of the Navstar 24 rubidium clock (serial no. 63) and the Navstar 29 cesium clock (serial no. K2).

Figure 18

The Navstar orbital positions for both clocks were computed using the precise post-fit ephemerides supplied by the National Imagery and Mapping Agency (NIMA). The frequency offset history of the Navstar 24 rubidium clock has been plotted as the upper curve on *Figure 18*, and the Navstar 29 cesium clock plotted as the lower curve. The total frequency change observed for this rubidium clock was in excess of $2 \text{ pp}10^{10}$ during this one-year time span, indicating the presence of a significant drift coefficient. The frequency offset history for the Navstar 29 cesium clock indicates no measurable drift and appears as a constant frequency offset in *Figure 18*.

Figure 19 presents the frequency stability history of the Navstar 24 rubidium clock using the Hadamard variance as an estimator, with a 120-sample moving-average window.

Figure 19

The initial frequency stability history estimate was 5.8×10^{-14} for a one-day stability. This clock showed a gradual improvement to 3×10^{-14} at the end of the data span. It should be noted that the rather large frequency drift has been removed through the use of the Hadamard variance that employs the second difference of the frequency offsets.

Figure 20 presents the frequency stability history of the Navstar 29 cesium clock using the Hadamard variance as an estimator, with a 120 sample moving-average window.

Figure 20

The frequency stability shows a near-constant frequency stability of some 8×10^{-14} for a one-day frequency stability.

Figure 21 presents estimates of the frequency stability for the Navstar 24 rubidium clock and the Navstar 29 cesium clock using the Allan variance as the estimator. The sample times evaluated vary from one day up to 12 days. For a one-day sample time, frequency stability estimates of 2.8×10^{-13} and 8×10^{-14} were measured for the rubidium and cesium clocks, respectively. For a 12-day sample time, the frequency estimates were 3.2×10^{-12} and 2×10^{-14} .

Figure 21

Figure 22 presents estimates of the frequency stability for the Navstar 24 rubidium clock and the Navstar 29 cesium clock using the Hadamard variance as the estimator.

Figure 22

For a one-day sample time, frequency stability estimates of 3.8×10^{-14} and 7×10^{-14} were measured for the rubidium and cesium clocks, respectively. For a 12-day sample time, the frequency estimates were 1.3×10^{-13} and 1.9×10^{-14} , respectively.

Both clocks meet their respective GPS performance specifications for a one-day sample time; however, there is a significant difference between the frequency stability estimates obtained using the Allan variance and the Hadamard variance as estimators of frequency stability. For the cesium clocks, little change was measured between values obtained using the Allan and Hadamard estimators. There was a significant difference observed for the frequency stability estimates obtained for the rubidium clock. This difference can be attributed to the known drift characteristics of this type of atomic clock.

NAVSTAR FREQUENCY STABILITY

Estimates of the one-day frequency stability for each of the Navstar clocks that were operational on 31 December 1996 are presented in Figure 23. The frequency stability estimates were computed using all available data for a four-month span, from 1 September 1996 through 31 December 1996. The Navstar orbital positions were computed using the precise post-fit ephemerides that were supplied by NIMA. The frequency stability estimates were computed using the Allan variance with no correction for drift.

Figure 23

Of the 25 clocks that were operational, 22 were cesium frequency standards. The clocks on Navstars 19, 24, and 31 are rubidium frequency standards. The frequency stability of all Block II Navstar clocks, with no correction for linear drift, was between $5.4 pp10^{14}$ and $2.2 pp10^{13}$. Twenty-three of the Navstar clocks had fre-

quency stability estimates that were between $5.4 pp10^{14}$ and $1.2 pp10^{13}$ for a one-day sample time. The contribution of a "typical" Navstar clock to the GPS error budget, after one day with no update by the MCS, would be on the order of 2.6 meters.

CONCLUSIONS

The results presented demonstrate that the frequency stability of several Navstar atomic clocks could be stationary, or time-invariant, for time spans of up to several years during the useful life of the clock. Frequency stability history analysis of these clocks can be used to detect and measure significant changes in frequency stability using moving average estimators of the Allan and Hadamard variances. The frequency stability history analysis can also be used to identify the maximum data length over which a given clock has stationary increments. The time resolution of the stationary increments is improved by the use of multiple features that may be present in the clock data, such as abrupt changes in the drift, or by correlation of the frequency stability history with other data. Each stationary increment is then used to compute segmented frequency stability profiles that accurately characterize the performance of these clocks for the specified time span.

Of the 25 Navstar clocks that were operational at the end of the year, the nominal frequency stability was estimated to be $1 pp10^{13}$ for a one-day sample time.

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